

D5.1 Online Communication Campaign Design and contents

WP 5 - Dissemination and Sustainability

Version 7 – 22.11.2019

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Preamble

The current Deliverable report consists a revised version of the initial D5.1 “Online Communication Campaign Design & Contents” report submitted by “Regional Environmental Center for Central and Eastern Europe – REC” on the 29th of May 2018. The revision was requested during the 1st EC review meeting in Brussels, September 2019. It performed by ViLabs WP Leader and anointed leader of the corresponding Project Task.

According to the comments of the reviewers, the initial (submitted by REC) document presented an abstract of the project, for no reason. It was missing its Section 1 Introduction and Overall Strategy wholly. It should also contain a section for the Conclusions. The document needed an overall revision. In addition, the dissemination and exploitation plan needed to be updated.

Thus, the following revisions took place:

Change of responsible Author and organisation holding the lead. Update on the Document information table, update on Document History Table, Insert of captions to all tables, images & graphics. Update of the introduction section. Update of overall Dissemination Strategy section, containing information on the real strategy that was/is followed. A new chapter on Social media strategy. New Chapter on Sustainability, Exploitation and Replication, containing brief information relevant to the sustainability, exploitation and replication of the project outputs and the interconnection with the dissemination activities described in this report deliverable. A new chapter – Conclusions. Inclusion of Annexes. An overall review with small revisions was also conducted.

Abstract

The Families_Share project offers a bottom-up solution in the form of a co-designed platform supporting families to share time and tasks related to childcare, parenting, after-school and leisure activities and other household tasks — with a particular focus on low-income families. The project also aspires to engage with the elderly by involving them in childcare activities and by offering them support in shopping and administrative tasks, but also by involving them in family events. To achieve this objective, the project borrows and integrates the concepts of time banking, capitalising on consortium members' existing digital social innovations in the childcare field. It also exploits the potential of information and communication technology (ICT) networks to increase participatory innovation by encouraging self-organising neighbourhoods.

Funded under the Information and Communication Technologies programme of Horizon 2020's Industrial Leadership component, and its call for collective awareness platforms for sustainability and social innovation, the project is developing a social networking and awareness-raising platform dedicated to encouraging childcare and work/life balance. The platform capitalises on neighbourhood networks and enables citizens to come together to share tasks, time and skills relevant to childcare and after-school education/leisure, where these have become unaffordable in times of stagnation and austerity.

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Executive Summary

This document provides an overview of the dissemination and campaign strategy of the Families_Share project, including information about the identification and implementation of the communication approach (the various dissemination channels, tools and materials used for dissemination purposes) as well as a preliminary approach over the sustainability, exploitation and replication of the project results.

The project adopts a dynamic dissemination plan from the very beginning of the project in order to:

- **Raise awareness** about the Families_Share project and approach, the benefits and opportunities for **local communities** and target stakeholders
- Increase **engagement** and encourage the involvement of targeted stakeholders in the project activities, especially during the **co-design activities** for the development of the Families_Share Platform
- Communicate the project results and **ensure** the **sustainability – exploitation** and **replication** of the Families_Share outputs after the completion of the project.

This report was developed for outlining the overall project dissemination strategy but also for reporting and assessing the implemented activities for reaching its dissemination objectives and target audience. This plan will be reviewed and updated on a regular basis for assessing new dissemination opportunities that are likely to emerge during the course of the project.

The provided communication and dissemination plan covers branding, the project website, social media channels, electronic newsletters and press releases as well as project's dissemination materials such as leaflets/brochures. The monitoring of dissemination activities provides information for the overall targets of the dissemination plan.

1 Introduction

This document includes a detailed action plan that sets a timeline and responsibilities for the project's dissemination and communication activities. It defines the primary and secondary target groups of the project and describes the dissemination channels and tools that will be deployed.

This action plan covers the first project period, and it will be updated on after the first project review, potentially in month 22-23 (October - November 2019) in order to correspond to the second implementation phase and the needs relevant to sustainability.

A procedure for monitoring and evaluation of dissemination activities, using specific Key Performance Indicators, is also defined as part of the Plan.

1.1 Intended Audience

This document consists of the plan of dissemination activities that will take place during the project lifespan. This document is aimed to be a practical tool for the project's dissemination manager as well as for all project partners to efficiently develop their individual and collective dissemination and communication activities and contribute to the overall objectives of the project.

In addition, the document can be used as guide - practical tool for "Horizon2020" – "Horizon Europe" dissemination managers of ongoing - future projects, who will be willing to explore our successful strategy and capitalise on it, as well as a relevant to dissemination guide for the reviewers of the European Commissions.

Ending, the current deliverable report can be used by any possible future replicator of the Families_Share approach and Families_Share Application.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is structured into the following 6 sections: Chapter 1 "Introduction" introduces the intended audience of the document and its structure. Chapter 2 "Dissemination, Communication and engagement Strategy" describes target groups, communication messages, channels and tools and planning and evaluation. Chapter 3 provides information on the "Social Media Strategy" that was followed during this period. Chapter 4 consists of an introduction to Sustainability, Exploitation and replication activities and is followed by Chapter 5 "Monitoring and Evaluation for the dissemination activities. Finally, Chapter 6 consists of the conclusions of this deliverable report. Two Annexes containing templates for reports and templates for presentations are also available.

2 Dissemination, Communication and engagement strategy

Dissemination and communication activities are essential for the success of the Families_Share project, as they will engage stakeholders and broadcast the knowledge and experience gained in the project in order to maximise its benefit to the European society.

The dissemination strategy will focus on the promotion of the project activities and results to attract the target audience, to raise awareness and engage stakeholders in project activities. A concrete dissemination plan will provide guidelines to consortium partners for organising their dissemination and communication activities within their national contexts. A common storyline around Families_Share will be developed which will be reflected in all project materials, including the customised messages, visuals and the videos that will be tailor-made for the project. All partners will support the dissemination of the project, its goals and outcomes, to raise awareness, maximise impact and exploitation.

A clear definition of all the dissemination strategy components follows in the next sections and provides the basis for all the dissemination and communication activities that will be implemented in Families_Share.

In addition, to achieve the project objectives from a dissemination point of view, the dissemination and communication strategy will follow the below phases:

- **Awareness-oriented phase:** This phase starts from the beginning of the project and runs up to its completion in order to raise awareness of the project, its objectives and activities.
- **Output-oriented phase:** This phase starts as soon as the first output of the projects are available and aims to promote them so as to allow stakeholders and final beneficiaries to get to know the projects achievements and the related benefits.
- **Sustainability-oriented phase:** This phase starts later in the project through preparatory activities that will contribute to the actual sustainability of the project results after its completion. Dissemination in this respect aims to support the overall sustainability activities by promoting to potential stakeholders.

To reach these goals, this document includes a roadmap and guidelines for dissemination performed by consortium partners during the project period.

The main elements of this strategy will be detailed in the following sections to provide the basis for all dissemination and communication activities that will be implemented during the project.

The main elements are:

- Target groups
- Dissemination messages
- Tools and channels
- Planning and evaluation

2.1 Project Dissemination & Communication Approach

Project dissemination plan follows the 6W approach. The 6W approach identifies:

- **Why communicate** – For efficient dissemination and communication, it is very important to understand what the objectives of the related activities are. This is done in the view of the main objectives of the whole project, as well as the objectives of the various project WPs/main activities.
- **Communicate What** – Regular dissemination requires the identification of project messages that can be diffused to the recipients (targeted stakeholders). These can be general project information, announcements, dissemination of findings or other.
- **Communicate to Whom** – Dissemination actions will target different stakeholders who have to be adequately identified so to be able to locate and properly address them.
- **Communicate hoW** – For efficient dissemination, it is important to understand the role of different project partners in this process, as well as the various communication tools to be applied to reach diverse groups.
- **Communicate Where** – A range of communication channels will be used to maximize the outreach of the dissemination activities, including project workshops, social media and others.
- **Communicate When** – The dissemination must run throughout the duration of the project, with long-lasting and scheduled actions, taking advantage of all communication opportunities that arise.

2.1.1 Objectives of the dissemination strategy

As already mentioned, this document aims to provide a clear description of the Dissemination strategy that will be adopted by Families_Share.

The main purpose of the dissemination strategy is to formalize all communication and dissemination activities planned in the framework of the project, to set out the main dissemination tools, to provide guidelines on the overall approach among the partners and to ensure that information is shared with appropriate audiences on a timely basis and by the most effective means.

More specifically, the objectives of the dissemination plan are:

- to identify target groups and analyze their communication needs
- to establish and maintain mechanisms for effective and timely communication and dissemination
- to establish core messages of the project, to be disseminated to the target groups
- to coordinate all levels and types of communication in relation to the project
- to define the timing of dissemination activities
- to define partners' responsibilities in dissemination activities
- to prepare the ground for ensuring sustainability after its completion

The Dissemination strategy is intended to be a live document, which will continuously be enriched with the forthcoming project's achievements and contributions from partners.

2.2 Why Communicate

Dissemination and communication activities are essential for the success of the Families_Share project, as they engage stakeholders and broadcast the knowledge and experience, that is to be gained in the project in order to maximise its benefit to European society. The dissemination strategy focuses on the promotion of the project activities and results to attract the target audience and to raise awareness and engage stakeholders in project activities.

2.3 Communicate to Whom

The dissemination and communication of Families_Share aim to raise awareness about work/life balance and social innovation in childcare among primary and secondary target groups.

Due to the participatory nature of the proposed project, a much-diversified combination of audiences, including citizens, municipal departments, businesses, NGOs technological developers and policymakers, and interested individuals in the area of digital social innovation and work/ life balance are the targets of the dissemination activities. Understanding the target groups in terms of their requirements, motivation and expectations is essential in the Families_Share dissemination strategy. The identification of target groups will not stop at the planning stage of a project; all partners and especially the relevant task leading partner, will continue to identify communities and organisations that could potentially be interested in the achievements and determine whether any modifications would be required in order to further support the exploitation of the project results. The targets for dissemination activities have been divided into the following categories, reflecting different needs and diverse interests in the Families_Share project.

Parents with young children residing in 6 cities of 4 countries of the CityLabs who serve as one of the primary participants. Business and professionals working in day-care and afterschool activities, teachers of primary schools, will also be a core group to find ways to directly cooperate with CityLabs. For academia and policymakers, the results of the Families_Share CityLabs can inform further research and regulatory integration to encourage and support similar future initiatives. The secondary target groups will be involved in more general awareness-raising about the Families_Share project to gain the attention and the support of the wider society especially those subgroups which might be interested in certain social or technological aspects of this innovation.

- The general public: the Families Share overall impact will go beyond the project's duration: by achieving behavioural change and raising awareness about social sharing through digital innovation,
- Families_Share will contribute to a large societal change that will improve the living conditions towards a healthier and happier lifestyle and will increase the resilience of European cities.

2.3.1 Primary Stakeholders

Families Share will have a direct impact on:

Primary Stakeholders		
Participant categories	Current situation-needs	Dissemination goals
Citizens: parents with young children (ages 3 to 11) resident in the 6 CityLab locations (Employees and workers with unstable working hours and precarious contracts, working mothers, fathers and their families, unprivileged groups, people of low literacy skills, elderly)	Due to the limited day-care and after school activity opportunities, they need assistance and a place where their children can spend time, play and learn	Raise awareness about Families_Share and its benefits in their everyday lives. They need to learn what they can do to co-design and later use the services of the new platform.
Childcare centres, child-friendly venues willing to host co-playing groups, babysitters, professionals trained in children's free time activities as potential volunteers	They need to raise awareness about their services and be connected to more parents with children in the target age groups	Raise awareness about Families_Share and encourage them to host or participate in co-design and co-playing activities
Academia	They need to learn more about how social innovation in childcare affects the development of children and their communities	Raise awareness about the output, especially research results coming from the experiences from co-design and co-play.
Policymakers	They need more information about social innovation in childcare to make more accommodating policies to social innovation not yet covered by existing regulations	Raise awareness about Families_Share and how social innovation in childcare can complement as an affordable alternative the currently available daycare/schooling options.

Table 1 - Primary Stakeholders

2.3.2 Secondary Stakeholders

In parallel, Families_Share will have an indirect impact on a broader audience:

Secondary Stakeholders	
Target group categories	Dissemination goals
Local authorities (Mayor's offices, town councils) Ministries under which education and childcare belong, municipal departments,	Raise awareness about Families_Share and its benefits in providing an alternative to conventional day-care for those in their constituency who have limited access to it.
NGOs and businesses also engaged in social innovation, preferably in childcare	Raise awareness about Families_Share and share it as a best practice in social innovation in childcare. Families_Share results and outcomes will be communicated to a large public and will help improve the business models in the social sector.
Technological developers also engaged in social innovation	Raise awareness about the output, especially research results coming from the experiences from co-design.
General public Mass media	Raise awareness about Families_Share and sharing success stories on how social innovation in childcare can complement as an affordable alternative positively impact society. The general public should also be encouraged to participate in this project and other initiatives beyond the project's time period.
Participants of other CAPs projects	Families_Share will create bridges with and will use their networks to mutually maximise the impact

Table 2 - Secondary Stakeholders

2.4 Communicate What - Communication messages

After considering the target groups contexts and needs, the guidelines and key messages of the project are to be developed.

- Messages should be clear and appropriate for the target group.
- Messages should be tailored to the target group relevant to their needs and context.
- Provide accurate and up-to-date information about the project and its developments.
- Encourage long term engagement, (e.g. using CityLab and digital platform beyond the project lifetime)

Families Share will leverage on its approach based on co-design and co-creation also in shaping the project's communication messages: networks of parents involved in the 6 City Labs will contribute shaping the main communication messages along with the duration of the project. The teasers which are proposed below can be considered as a starting point, as the messages will be exposed to local communities and be adapted/re-framed along the way thanks to inputs from the participating groups of parents and stakeholders.

2.4.1 Key message goals:

- **Build commitment:** Through co-design workshops and co-playing events **change attitudes and create emotional involvement of citizens and of the broader society.**
- **Make Families_Share part of citizen's everyday live: encourage the regular use of the Families_Share platform** through the communities to organize co-playing activities
- **Share knowledge about Families_Share:** through online and offline activities with members of the Public and Private sectors to inform decision-makers and academics approach to childcare and work/life balance related innovations
- **Impact on the academic community:** Families Share has interesting potential outcomes from a research perspective within disciplines such as sociology, political economy, STS (Science and Technology Studies), Human-Computer Interaction and similar.

2.4.2 Message examples:

Target groups/ participants	
Participants	Dissemination message
Citizens	<p><i>Families_Share offers an affordable solution for childcare and contributes positively to work/life balance.</i></p> <p><i>After-school activities have become a luxury. Families_Share leads community collaboration to change this.</i></p> <p><i>Communities and neighbourhoods collectively share care and educational activities and in doing so, increase solidarity and social cohesion. This benefits children as well who are exposed to different experiences and models.</i></p>
NGOs, and businesses also engaged in social innovation, preferably in childcare	<p><i>Balancing work and family life has become increasingly challenging in the last decade in Europe. The economic crisis impacted both labour market conditions and welfare provisions.</i></p> <p><i>The Families_Share project offers a bottom-up solution in the form of a co-designed platform supporting families to share time and tasks related to childcare.</i></p> <p><i>It exploits the potential of information and communication technology (ICT) networks to increase participatory innovation by encouraging self-organising activities.</i></p> <p><i>Families Share offers the opportunity to make your (or your company's) skills and competences in childcare available to larger communities of families interested in using shared professional care.</i></p>
Academia	<p><i>As a result of budget cuts in public welfare expenditure, in many European cities, the available childcare services are insufficient, putting families with children under significant pressure.</i></p> <p><i>Unemployment rates have risen (mainly in male-dominated sectors), while more women (including mothers) are working on a part-time basis and precarious contracts are increasingly widespread, with many workers entering re-qualification schemes.</i></p>
General public Mass media	<p><i>Members of neighbourhoods and communities are often isolated. Families_Share Citylabs aim to change this.</i></p> <p><i>The Families_Share project borrows and integrates the concepts of time banking, capitalizing on consortium members' existing digital social innovations in the childcare field.</i></p>

2.5 Communicate How: Dissemination Channels and Tools

The dissemination of Families_Share will integrate several forms of media. Some channels and activities are expected to create higher visibility than others. This section introduces how different media channels and tools will be used to support the project in terms of visibility.

The following **online channels** will be used for dissemination of information on the implementation of the project, its activities and its results: Families_Share will use the project website, partners' websites, mailing lists or mail database lists, E-Newsletters, online meetings, webinars, social media and the success stories videos/interviews that will be used to raise awareness and enhance the participatory design and implementation of the project activities.

In parallel, the following **offline channels** will be exploited for dissemination and communication activities so as to reach out all the target stakeholders and audience: brochures, press releases, seminars, workshops, academic papers, conferences, awareness-raising events, roundtables and local info points.

All in all, Families_Share will capitalize on the networks of its consortium to multiply its reach. At local/national, European and international level, all partners will be involved and engaged in increasing the dissemination process and communicating the project to the respective stakeholders. Families_Share will establish new synergies with other EU Funded CAPs projects, established initiatives, relevant stakeholders, NGOs, local authorities and other networks to exchange ideas and increase mutual learning.

2.5.1 Project Branding

The development of the Families_Share brand was a significant step to create a unified, easily recognisable visual identity for the project. The project logo serves as a symbol for a family which is open and sharing, the key concepts behind the project. In other visual communications, families and households are usually represented as closed -groups while in our logo we aimed at recalling openness; we also pay attention to avoid stereotyped representations of the concept of "family" specifically with the effort to represent gender-neutral characters in order to avoid biases.

2.5.2 Project Website

(<http://families-share.eu/>)

The purpose of the website is to serve as the central source of information about the project, update on CityLabs and project news. Apart from the main site, the subsites organized by CityLabs will provide localized information about the implementation of activities. The CityLab portals, as the consortium calls them, are used as the national channel for all CityLabs. They are translated in the national languages; they contain information about the citylab, the activities, the available spaces, about the Families_Share application along with the link to download the application, online guidelines and Frequently asked questions and of course documents to download (Guidelines, FAQs and such). Users can also contact each CityLab via these portals via the emails that were set for each Citylab or via the social media accounts of each CityLab.

The website will be used as the main online tool of the project; it will foster awareness-raising and engagement and be promoted on social media as well as on digital and hard copy promotional materials and publications.

Website structure

Figure 1: Families_Share Website structure

➤ **Main steps:**

- **Site map**
- **Wireframe**
- **Design**
- **Content**
- **Static content (e.g., About): drafted based on the proposal text**
- **News & Events: based on regular contribution**
- **Members area**

Image 1: Website Home Page

The website will be maintained throughout the project cycle and will remain active for at least 3 years after the official completion of the Families_Share Project. At the initial stage, the website provided static content and some news articles and events. Currently, CityLab portals have been developed featuring content in national languages to support the activities of the pilot partners.

Welcome to the Families_Share project website!

Families_Share offers a bottom-up solution to work/life balance by supporting families with childcare, parenting advice and after-school activities—with a particular focus on low-income families. To achieve this objective the project borrows and integrates concepts from the Time Banks and Social Streets models, and seeks to harness the potential of ICT networks and mobile technologies to increase the effectiveness of participatory innovation in the sense of self-organizing neighbourhoods.

The project is developed in 6 Pilot Cities in 5 countries and involves parents of children aged 3–11 that live in the same neighbourhoods in the 6 Pilot cities (Bologna, Gyor, Kortrijk, Thessaloniki, Trento, Venice). Though, they often already participate in parents' groups, parents often fail to formulate organized motivated communities that share knowledge and services. The Families_Share project enables them to meet locally and co-design internationally the Families_Share Share Platform that will allow them to post challenges, share learning sources, meet up, match their needs and profiles and agree on timesharing schemes for mutual support in childcare and after-school activities to improve their work/life balance and increase the quality of learning opportunities for their kids.

[LEARN MORE →](#)

Image 2: Families_Share Website Introduction message

Image 3: Families_Share Website News section

Access to the Members Area will be based on the “https protocol”. Hhttps protects the privacy and security of our users by encrypting the communication between the browser that the user is using and the server, which hosts the website. Via this encryption, both data exchanged between users and website but also the integrity of the website are more protected.

In terms of specific tailored security measures: The **security issue** is the first that was taken into account when we were building this website. Brute force attacks, hacks on retrieving usernames, hacks on logins etc. are blocked. Plus, there is a software firewall running behind the website for preventing “suspicious” IPs from accessing the website. The identification of the “suspicious” IPs is being made automatically; “suspicious” actions are also being logged. Vulnerabilities that exist in other websites have been extinguished. The security section is being updated constantly.

Ending, the website is SEO friendly, and after a period of time, google results will bring the website to higher ranks, this does not only depend on the website itself, back-links must be

also included from other websites, e.g. partner websites, links on social media etc. This procedure is a 2-way procedure. Moreover, we have implemented Libraries so keywords will be easily searchable by Google.

In addition, most of the project partners have developed their own Families_Share subpages within their organisational websites to promote and communicate their activities in their national languages.

Case of [ViLabs](#):

Image 4 - ViLabs Website - Families_Share Information

Case of [SmartVenice](#):

Image 5 - Smart Venice Website - Families_Share Information

Case of [FBK](#):

Image 6 - FBK Website - Families_Share Information

Case of [Urbanista](#):

Image 7- Urbanista Website - Families_Share Information

2.5.3 Promotional materials

Brochures: Brochures will be small booklets that will be made in line with the Families_Share visual identity. They will provide general information about the Families share, including issues it aims to address and solutions it offers. They will list and describe the CityLabs and list the consortium partners. Their aim is to provide information on target groups participating in offline events (meetings, workshops, conferences).

Promotional and “Success story” videos: short (about 1-2 minutes long) will be made to promote the project and feature Success stories from the various CityLabs and be uploaded to the Families_Share website and YouTube channel. At least 6 videos (one for each CityLab) are planned as an effective communication tool. They will be prepared during the first evaluation phase in order to exploit success stories as interviews with Families_Share participants. They will be realized as low-budget, but professional video-clips in local languages subtitled in English (and possibly other languages). Additional information can be found in the corresponding deliverable, Deliverable D.5.2. “Success stories Videos” – Project Month 20.

2.5.4 E-Newsletters and Press Releases

Image 8 - Families_Share E-Newsletter

Electronic newsletters will be sent out every 6 months from M1 to M34 to the Families_Share community mostly consisting of parents, caretakers and other subscribers for whom the project is interesting and relevant. The topics could include key actions of the project, key workshops/events/conferences/exhibitions where Families_Share has been presented or has organised, news about relevant projects, activities and events. All versions of the Newsletters will be prepared in English (but content in national language can also be used) and distributed electronically through the [Mailchimp](#) marketing platform. An initial template is ready and can be found in the figure below.

Press releases will target the mass media and the general public to raise awareness about Families_Share as a socially innovative project in the area of work/life balance and childcare. A press release is more formal and aiming

at being released in national or European newspapers and e-magazines. Families_Share project will publish frequently short and concise texts to disseminate through mailing lists and database lists in order to keep the audience informed and will be issued in a regular basis in order to announce and report about Families_Share activities, events and findings. Families_Share project will prepare press releases to raise awareness and disseminate information about the project. Press releases will be prepared for important project events or relevant milestones. Press releases will be published on the website, on social media channels and through press contacts of the partner organizations (in translation where necessary).

Image 9 - Press Release Template

2.5.5 Academic papers and policy briefs

As the experiences of the Citylabs are gathered, academic papers will be submitted to academic journals. Policy briefs towards the end of the project will be produced to inform policymakers on how childcare could be improved based on the outcomes of the Families_Share project and on the impacts of digital social innovation on childcare services, work-life balance and local social cohesion.

2.5.6 Active participation via the CAPSSI initiative

CAPSSI “Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation initiative is promoted by the European Commission and empowered via coordination and support activities provided by the ChiC, Coordinating high-Impact for CAPS, project (<https://capssi.eu/about/>). By its very beginning, Families_Share has taken an active part in the CAPSSI initiative and its activities, like the monthly CAPS Teleconferences, exchanges of knowledge and approaches.

Moreover, on the 6th and 7th of June 2018, Families_Share participated at the DSI FAIR 2018, where the Project coordinator presented the project to the rest CAPS Projects and

initiatives attending the fair. As an active part of the community, Families_Share will seek to support the dissemination of the initiative as well as to establish contact and collaboration with other relevant CAPS projects in order to maximise the potential reach and share knowledge within the CAPS community.

CAPS Project uses the hashtag #capssi as well as the “@” mention along with the CAPSSI logo to establish a dissemination network and maximize dissemination impact. Families_Share follows the same tactic. Ending, during the lifecycle of the project, Families_Share seeks to provide information to the joint newsletter as well as to publish more articles on the CAPSSI community under the CAPSSI website.”

2.6 Disseminate where

This section defines the main online and offline channels of communication. These include the project website, social media, third-party events, project workshops, partners’ own websites/social networks and other channels where targeted audiences can be reached.

From the beginning of the project, partners were required to provide with a list of existing contacts of support organizations and projects and also with third party events, conferences, they are planning to attend and disseminate the project.

2.6.1 Project Events and Activities

- Networking, meetings and events include: Info points: parents, the general public, meetings with local authorities, ministries and municipal departments, businesses, NGOs technological developers and policymakers
- One local co-design workshop per city per co-designing phase (14 in total)> approx. 35 attendees each
- Two international co-design workshops per co-designing phase (2 in total)> approx. 15 attendees each
- Bi-monthly meetups (world-café/ social dinners or brunches: 3 meetups at phase 1, one meeting
- 1 awareness-raising event per country reaching the target participants of 80 people at each pilot location.
- Local exploitation roundtables at the end of the project
- Final Conference hosted at large event on digital social innovation attracting approx. 500 attendees

2.6.2 Third-party Events

Event/conference/ Journal/magazine/media	Target Group	Type of participation
ICT 2018	ICT industry and policymakers involved in digital agenda issues	Project and platform presentation
EIP SCC Annual events 2018, 2019	Multiple stakeholders (cities, industry, academia, NGOs)	Presentation at the Citizens Cluster meeting, networking at the General Assembly
European Conference on Information Systems	Peer collaboration via CAPS	Oral /presentation
International Social Innovation Research Conference	Governance	Oral presentation
Web 2.0 Tools (incl. T&W Blog, Twitter, YouTube and Facebook)	General public	Regular publications of results and project promotion
ACM International conference on Communities & Technologies	Researcher	Oral presentation
Annual ESPAnet Conference	Researchers, political stakeholders	Oral presentation

Table 3: Visibility opportunities, target groups and types of participation

2.7 Dissemination When - Dissemination Time plan

Task 5.1 “Definition of the Communication and Dissemination Plan & Dissemination activities” also includes monitoring and evaluation activities. The objectives of these monitoring and evaluation activities are to provide concrete evidence on the effectiveness of dissemination as well as insights on the implemented strategy and ways to maximize its reach and impact.

The dissemination time plan was drafted from the beginning of the project and will be regularly assessed during the course of the project. To allow adequate monitoring of the external communication activities and understand the impact generated by these activities, partners are requested to report constantly (and periodically) the activities and actions carried out.

The dissemination time plan illustrates the dissemination activities of the project based upon a month-by-month delivery schedule. The scheduling of these activities is closely aligned with key project deliverables.

Image 10 - Dissemination Time plan 1/3

Image 11 - Dissemination Time plan 2/3

Image 12 - Dissemination Time plan 3/3

3 Social Media strategy

Social media channels are an integral part of our dissemination and communication strategy as they provide the chance to get connected and reach regions and stakeholders all over the world. The aim of this section is to present the basic elements of the social media strategy and its channels that will be used for the project. Our overall approach was based on the figure below, which represents our specific strategy using social media as a modern tool, which is constantly updated and aligned to changes and new features, to help us promote the project and its activities and explore new possibilities for reaching the relevant audience. The general approach is easy and quite simple, and it is described in the figure below. The figure shows the path the project will follow in order to identify the stakeholders, the relevant channels and increase the impact. There are 3 steps: Boot up, set up and manage

up.

Figure 2: Social media strategy steps

3.1 Social media Tools

In the planning stages of the Families_Share project, it was decided to build social media presence to represent the consortium members, the CityLabs and the project in an integrated way. Its main goals are to bring attention to the project website, amplify its content, support communication and impact creation of City Labs and encourage participation in the CityLab communities. Four social media channels will be used: Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and YouTube.

The channels were carefully chosen by ViLabs, and they were presented to the Consortium during the kick-off meeting to finalise the decision and the targeting based on the partners' experience from their individual accounts and networks. The following table was developed as initial thoughts before setting up the accounts, and it was discussed as a basis with the Consortium.

Channel	Rationale	Frequency
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The most popular network. Most of the partners maintain Facebook pages which can provide us with our first audience. Many features to capitalize on including video posting, events, photos, carousels, promoting the open calls in different ways without a limitation in characters. There is the option to use advertisements to promote the page and the application. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Post twice a week. More if the available content is critical.
Twitter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A popular network with short and concise messages. Easy to use. Many projects & relevant stakeholders use it. Project partners have accounts with many followers and dedicated audience. Based on past experience, Twitter is a successful tool for projects; Helps to live blogging during events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Almost on a daily basis, depending on the content. Two tweets per week, if there is no occasion.
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Add useful content, e.g. articles, newsletters etc. Tag organisations so they are able to share the news with their professional network. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When an occasion to motivate the business, network presents itself. At least one post per

		two weeks
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Useful to share the project videos. No wide dissemination of the channel per se, but of the individual videos. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Before Month 20 for the success stories videos. After interviews or radio/TV broadcasts. In cases of webinars/teleconferences. When a video is available.

Table 4 - Selected Social Media channels

3.1.1 Facebook Page

Families_Share has a Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/familiesShare/>) which currently (time of the revision of the current deliverable report –November 2019) counts 540 “follows”. The project logo was used as a profile image, while a promotional video of parents (from our partner De Stuyverij) holding cards with the message “ *I am part of the family*”, accompanied by the project selected soundtrack, is used as the cover section of the Facebook page.

Image 13 - Families_Share Facebook Page

3.1.2 Twitter Profile

Project-related news and relevant articles from other sources in support of shared childcare and work-life balance will be tweeted. The target groups will be citizens of the pilot locations, the general public, municipal departments, businesses, NGOs technological developers.

The Twitter account (https://twitter.com/Families_Share), which currently has 183 followers, will be mainly used to promote participatory activities, local awareness-raising events, the exploitation tables and the project progress in general. It is a great tool to connect with most of our relevant stakeholders, which have already established a strong presence, and they are very enthusiastic about our tweets. A screenshot below presents the Twitter profile with the logo on the profile image and a tailored cover page, which makes the profile friendlier and warmer for the users, creating positive feelings about it. Users have access to a short description of the project as well as to the link leading to the project website.

Image 14 - Families_Share Twitter Profile

3.1.3 LinkedIn

LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/families-share/>) has a dual purpose for Families_Share. It is mainly used to promote professional content and to promote the project activities, but it is also used to motivate users/individuals to reach the members of

the consortium and find representatives of the project in their countries, as almost all the members of the consortium have connected to the public page with their profiles.

Image 15 - Families_Share LinkedIn Account

4 Sustainability, Exploitation and Replication

WP5 – “Dissemination and Sustainability” is strongly oriented to the dissemination activities supporting the project during the implementation of its activities, as well as to activities oriented directly to the actual sustainability of the project outputs along with the creation of the expected and needed ground, that will support the further exploitation and replication of those outputs, even after the official completion of the Families_Share project.

Besides specific tasks under WP5 such as Task 5.3 “Exploitation and replication plan”, it is obvious and well perceived by all members of the consortium that all dissemination efforts and all the tasks relevant to this WP do take into account and act upon the factors of sustainability – exploitation and replication. Thus, all dissemination and communication activities will be targeted, interconnected or at least lead in a way to this specific target.

If anything, this is the final target – the ultimate goal of dissemination actions and of all projects, which base their activities in co-design practises and the exploration of new ways to support communities via the use of ICT.

Hence, the consortium members consider Sustainability and replication of the Families_Share project and all outputs as factors of great importance and have provided with initial individual exploitation plans, while they are planning to work on the “in-house sustainability” even before the official initiation of the corresponding task.

The main ambition of Families_Share is to provide a European wide solution for improving families work-life balance by co-designing and using a collaborative platform. There are many organisations and grassroots communities around Europe and globally that work towards this end, but mainly based on a more traditional approach and without exploiting the power of online networks. Families_Share offers a unique opportunity for them to make their activities more effective, engage more citizens and increase their impact. To this end Families_Share platform will be made available through a standard Open Source licence, so as to provide the opportunity to interested childcare organisations, companies, public authorities and other grassroots organisations to replicate, adopt and use it after the end of the project.

Our aim is to encourage and help as many stakeholders as possible to adopt the results of

To realize this objective, the project consortium will proceed the upcoming months with a concrete exploitation plan that will include specific directions for:

- Ensuring the sustainability and scaling of Families_Share activities and outputs in a national pilot context, by the project partners and existing communities of users after the end of the project.
- Supporting the expansion and replication of Families_Share in various geographical contexts around Europe, as well as in different application areas/target groups (people with disabilities and special needs, marginalized groups and such other).

Families_Share, with the overall objective to further increase the childcare solutions, support families and their work-life balance, create friendlier communities, develop new project ideas/business, change or update local and regional childcare policies around Europe.

5 Monitoring and Evaluation

The activities of the communication and dissemination of the project will be monitored and evaluated to provide evidence of its' progress and effectiveness. The activities will be regularly assessed during the project lifecycle. The table below summarizes the dissemination indicators of the project as a whole and targets for each period.

5.1 Website and social media targets

Dissemination Report	M18	M12	M18	M24	Projects Overall Target M34
General Dissemination Metrics					
Website traffic					
Page views	500	2000	10000	15000	30000
Downloads	0	0	300	600	1601
Social media					
Followers:					
Facebook	300	400	800	1000	1200
Twitter	30	70	100	250	500
LinkedIn	7	35	50	75	100
Numbers of shares/mentions:					
Facebook	20	50	90	140	200
Twitter	5	15	30	40	50
LinkedIn	1	3	5	7	10

Image 16 - Website and social media targets

5.2 Written publications, presentations and video targets

	M6	M12	M18	M24	Projects Overall Target M34
Press releases and newsletters					
Nr of Newsletters	1	2	3	4	6
Nr of Press releases	1	2	3	4	5
Scientific publications					
Number of papers submitted	0	0	0	0	1
Number of conference presentations	2	4	11	15	>19
Network contacts					
Number of network contact	0	1050	2100	3150	4200
Number of Videos	0	2	4	8	10

Image 17 - Written publications, presentations & video targets

5.3 Direct stakeholder engagement and policy impact targets

Project Specific Metrics	M6	M12	M18	M24	Project Overall Target M34
Outreach of awareness-raising campaign at EU level	0	0	400	800	12000
Number of policymakers and institutions representatives aware of the projects policy recommendations (at local, regional, national and international level)	0	0	0	0	>70
Number of citizens engaged in co-designing the Families_Share Platform and services	560	840	1750	2625	4200
Number of policies changed or updated by the project (local and regional level)	0	0	0	0	>3
Over 1500 people per city to be informed via the Families_Share CityLabs	100	300	600	1000	1500
1 offline event per CityLab organised to facilitate and support citizens' engagement to WP1 and WP3 (80 people each at physical meetings)	-	-	-	1 Awareness raising event	80 people per CityLab
Two international co-design workshops per co-designing phase (2 in total)	0	0	15	30	2 international workshops with 15 participants each
Final Conference	0	0	0	500	500

Image 18 - Direct stakeholder engagement & policy impact targets

6 Conclusions

This document provides an overview of the project dissemination, communication and engagement strategy, highlighting its key elements:

- The reason and objectives of communication and dissemination
- The project target groups
- The key communication messages
- The various dissemination channels and tools that will be used
- The offline dissemination opportunities (awareness-raising campaigns, meet-ups, events and such).
- The planning and evaluation of dissemination activities.
- The sustainability, exploitation and replication initial approach

The dissemination plan presented in this deliverable covers the initial strategy that was to be followed (and was actually followed) by the project and presents the progress achieved until M5 (the initial date of delivery). Partners will use (have used the strategy provided via) this document as the initial strategy which was constantly under evaluation. Any adjustments related to the dissemination plan together with progress in dissemination activities will be reported in the two periodic reports that are to be submitted to the European Commission (M18) and (M34). In addition, updates on the dissemination activities will be included in the relevant upcoming deliverables, D.5.3. “Report of awareness-raising campaign and events” and D5.4. “Report on Sustainability models and Exploitation Plan, and on Policies Recommendations”.

Annex A - Dissemination activities reporting template

Dissemination activities reporting

Guidelines: Before reporting any information, please, make sure to make a copy of this document and rename it with the name of the activity and your institution's acronym. Secure your file in the dedicated folder on Google Drive:

For further details or information, send an email to chatzimalis@vilabs.eu

Choose the type of the Dissemination and Communication activity you are reporting.

- Press Release
- Non-Scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularized publication)
- Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV, etc.)
- Video/Film
- Organization of a Conference
- Participation to a Conference
- Organization of a Workshop
- Participation to a Workshop
- Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop
- Organization of an Awareness Raising Event
- Training
- Exhibition
- Brokerage Event
- Pitch Event
- Trade Fair
- Participation in other activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects
- Flyer
- Social Media
- Website
- Other

Template for reporting a Families_Share Publication

General Information	
Title of publication	
Date published	
Website name / magazine name	
Description of the website / magazine	
Website/magazine URL	
Views access	

Pictures	(to be uploaded at project Facebook page)
Short description to be added under 'news' in the project's website	

Template for reporting the participation of Families_Share in events

General Information	Participation to a Conference
Name of event	
Date	
Location	
Event organizer	
Event website	
Description of the event (objectives, target audience etc.)	
Results	
Families_Share Partners attending the event	
Type of participation (brief descriptions of activities)	
Estimated number of participants reached**	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scientific community (higher education, research): ● Industry: ● Civil Society: ● General public: ● Policy Makers: ● Media: ● Investors: ● Customers: ● Other:
Indicate the distribution of men/women in percentage	
Pictures	Add one or two here! For the rest please make a folder with the name of the event that are relevant.
Remarks/Recommendations	
Website	
Short description to be added under 'news' in the project's website	

** Estimated number of persons reached: Complete the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of all dissemination activities. European Commission guidelines ask us to specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of the reported dissemination and communication activity, in each of the mentioned categories.

Annex B - Deliverables and presentation templates

MSWord template for reports:

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	780783	Acronym	FAMILIES_SHARE
Full Title	Families_Share ('Socializing and sharing time for work/ life balance through digital and social innovation')		
Topic	H2020 CAPS Topic: ICT---11---2017		
Funding scheme	IA Innovation Action		
Start Date	1/1/2018	Duration	34 months
Project URL	www.families-share.eu		
EU Project Officer	Loretta Anania		
Project Coordinator	Agostino Cortesi, UNIVE		
Deliverable	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX		
Work Package	XXXXXXX		
Date of Delivery	Contractual	MXXXX	Actual MXXX
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	X-XXX
Lead Beneficiary	XXXXXXXX		
Responsible Author	XXXXXX	Email	XXXXXXXX
	XXXXXXXX	Phone	XXXXXX
Contributor(s):	All partners		
Keywords	XXXXX, XXXXX, XXXXX		

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0				
1.1				
1.2				
2.0				

MS PowerPoint template for presentations on the consortium meetings.

This template consists of seven slides:

- Slide 1:** Title slide with fields for 'FAMILIES_SHARE', 'WP N', 'Task x', 'Title of the task', and 'Task number & ID'. Includes logos for the consortium and the European Union.
- Slide 2:** 'Task x.x Overview' with bullet points for 'Goals and objectives', 'List of Deliverables', and 'List of Milestones'.
- Slide 3:** 'Task x.x - Activity' with a bullet point 'Describe the activity'.
- Slide 4:** 'Task x.x Work plan' with a bullet point 'List the activities for the next 6 months' and a table with columns 'Task plan for the next 6 months', 'Deliverables to be produced by the partner', and 'Timeline'.
- Slide 5:** 'Task x.x Summary of Key Milestones' with a bullet point 'Describe the key milestones for the next six months including the partners involved and deadlines' and a table with columns 'Milestone', 'Leader', and 'Date'.
- Slide 6:** 'Task x.x Risks' with a bullet point 'Describe the main risks to be monitored in the next six months' and a table with columns 'Risk', 'Description', 'Impact', and 'Mitigation plan'.
- Slide 7:** 'Thank you' slide with a bullet point 'Contact details'.

MS PowerPoint template for presentations on activities/workshops/events.

This template consists of five slides:

- Slide 1:** Title slide for 'Families-Share project' with fields for 'Participant engagement', 'Second participant and engagement', 'Deliverable chain milestones', and 'TITLE OF EVENT'. Includes logos for the consortium and the European Union.
- Slide 2:** 'Introduction' slide with a central diagram and text: 'All these resources provide the project with an overview of the development of content and milestones and activities related to the project.' Includes a 'Impact' box.
- Slide 3:** 'City Labs' slide with sub-sections 'Families - Share' and 'City Labs' (participatory needs analysis, co-design and co-creation processes). Text: '> leading to the first Families_Share Platform prototype that will trigger socially innovative models for socialising children in urban neighbourhoods.' Includes logos for various partners.
- Slide 4:** 'Families-Share Platform' slide with sub-sections 'Functionalities & features' and 'Families-Share app'. Features include 'All families', 'Educational, leisure activities Quality time', 'Time management', 'Space management', and 'Responsive-iterative co-design'. Text: 'These services are the core of the platform'.
- Slide 5:** 'Thank you!' slide with logos for partners (Labs, amec, cyon, A.M.I.S.T., etc.) and social media links for Families_Share on Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter.